

THE INFLUENCE OF IMPACTOR SHAPE ON THE DAMAGE TO COMPOSITE LAMINATES

T. Mitrevski ¹, I.H. Marshall ¹, and R.S. Thomson ²

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Monash University
Clayton Campus, Wellington Rd, Clayton, Victoria, 3800, Australia*

² *Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Limited
506 Lorimer Street, Fishermen's Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia*

SUMMARY: The post-impact damage properties of composite laminates impacted by various impactor shapes are investigated herein. This investigation is a continuation of the research conducted in [1]. The effect of impactor shape under low-velocity conditions has been largely neglected since the use of hemispherical impactors has been predominantly investigated in past research. After impacting thin woven carbon/epoxy laminates using hemispherical, ogival and conical steel impactors all 12 mm in diameter using a drop weight test rig [1], various post-impact analysis techniques have been employed, such as non-destructive inspection (NDI) and microscopy to assess the effect of impactor shape on the resulting damage. The blunter hemispherical impactor produced the largest damage area dominated by delamination. The rather sharp conical impactor produced the most fibre breakage which resulted in a localised damage area and the largest indentation/penetration depth.

KEYWORDS: impactor shape, carbon/epoxy, microscopy, C-scan, low-velocity

INTRODUCTION

Low-velocity impacts can significantly reduce the residual strength of composite materials even when barely visible impact damage (BVID) is produced. Low-velocity impact testing simulates such accident scenarios as a dropped tool during maintenance. BVID can result in internal damage such as delamination and back-face splitting which can reduce the residual strength by as much as 60% [2-8].

In past research, the most common impactor shape used has been hemispherical, generally 12.7 mm (0.5 inch) diameter. However, a dropped tool on a composite panel during maintenance may not always impact the panel with a relatively blunt shape such as a hemisphere. In Mitrevski et al. [1], the effects of impactor shape were investigated using hemispherical, ogival and conical impactors using a drop weight test rig on thin quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates. It was found that the specimens impacted by the conical impactor absorbed the most energy and produced the largest indentation/penetration depth. The blunter hemispherical impactor produced the largest peak force and shortest contact duration. The damage threshold limit (DTL) was highest for the hemispherical impactor followed by the ogival and conical impactors respectively.

Lee, Cheon and Im [9] conducted low-velocity impact tests on simply supported sheet moulding compound (SMC) laminates using conical, flat, hemispherical, and semi-cylindrical impactors. They found that the different impactor shapes produced different damage

mechanisms in the SMC which directly affected the energy absorption characteristics of the material. Zhou, Lloyd and McGuirk [10] also found that changing the impactor shape changed the damage mechanism. Under static test conditions, Mines, Roach and Jones [11] found flat and hemispherical impactors produced larger delamination areas compared to a conical impactor in both woven and z-stitched laminates of varying thickness.

Using a hemispherical impactor 12.7 mm in diameter, Shyr and Pan [12] conducted low-velocity impacts on woven, non-woven and multiaxial warp-knit E-glass/polyester laminates. Using a metallographic microscope, they found that the structure of the fibres affected the delamination pattern and size. As a result of high stresses and indentation effects, fibre breakage was found in the top plies. The impact damage in the bottom layers was attributed to bending stresses which is supported by [13,14]. Cantwell and Morton [14] found that, in thin specimens, the damage initiated in the bottom layers, whereas with thick specimens, damage initiated in the top layers. The overall damage pattern through the thickness in composite materials generally follows a conical shape as found by [12,14,15].

The residual tensile and compressive strengths of composite laminates are influenced by the damage area and mechanisms induced by the impact [2-8]. Different impactor shapes will produce different damage mechanisms and areas in composite laminates; hence the residual properties of the material will change according to the impactor shape. It is therefore important to investigate the effects of different impactor shapes on the damage resistance and tolerance of composite laminates.

The Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS) in Melbourne, Australia, is presently conducting research into the damage resistance and tolerance of various composite materials as potential replacement panels for the F-111 aircraft [16]. Part of the project is to research the effect of impactor shapes and preload on the low-velocity impact response of woven carbon/epoxy composite laminates, which forms part of the present ongoing investigation.

The work presented here examines the low-velocity impact tolerance of carbon/epoxy laminates to various impactor shapes. Information obtained from optical micrographs, ultrasonic C-scans and thermography was used to examine the development of impact damage in the specimens. This will be followed in the future by in-plane tension tests to determine the residual load carrying capability of the specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimens were manufactured from the Advanced Composites Group medium temperature curing carbon-epoxy prepreg system (XMTM49-3). The prepreg was a 2x2 twill-weave HTA-5131 3k carbon fabric with an areal weight of 200 g/m². The panels were cured in an autoclave following a recommended cure cycle. Once cured, the panels were cut into specimens of 215 x 215 mm in dimension with an average thickness of 1.9 mm with the stacking sequence specified in Table 1. Aluminium end tabs were also bonded to the specimens to prevent matrix crushing and stress concentrations induced by the grips on the test rig.

Low-velocity impact tests were conducted using a guided drop-weight test rig developed at Monash University shown in Fig. 1 with the test program outlined in Table 1. A crosshead brake attached to the test rig prevents multiple impacts on the specimen by the impactor. The impactor consists of three parts, the crosshead, shank, and nose which can be changed. Three

steel nose shapes were used in the experiments, conical, ogival and hemispherical, all 12 mm in diameter as shown in Fig. 2.

Initial impact energies of 4 J and 6 J were used to impact the specimens by adjusting the height of the 4.325 kg impactor, which can be raised up to a maximum of 5 m. The shank has a diameter of 12 mm and a piezo-electric force transducer is attached to the shank to measure the force-time history. A metal strip attached to the crosshead passes through four optical sensors as the crosshead falls. These optical sensors trigger the data acquisition system and calculate the impact and rebound velocities. The specimens were clamped on all four edges to provide an impact area of 140 mm x 140 mm. The test-rig was designed with the added capability to provide simultaneous biaxial in-plane preload (tension/tension, compression/compression and tension/compression (shear)) during impact on the specimen. This is achieved through hydraulic rams located on both axes of the specimen. For further details on the test rig and its components refer to Whittingham et al. [17].

Figure 1: Drop weight test rig with biaxial preload capability

Figure 2: a) Hemispherical tip, b) ogival tip and c) conical tip, all 12 mm in diameter

Table 1: Impact conditions.

Stacking-Sequence	Impact Energy	Impactor Shape	Boundary Condition	Number of Specimens
[45,0,45,0] _s (Lay-up 1)	6 J	Conical	Fixed	4
		Ogival	Fixed	4
		Hemispherical	Fixed	4
[0,45,0,45] _s (Lay-up 2)	4 J	Conical	Fixed	5
		Ogival	Fixed	5
		Hemispherical	Fixed	5
[0,45,0,45] _s (Lay-up 2)	6 J	Conical	Fixed	4
		Ogival	Fixed	4
		hemispherical	Fixed	4

Damage areas were measured using two NDI techniques; ultrasonic C-scanning and flash thermography both conducted at the Defence Science and Technology Organisation (DSTO) in Melbourne, Australia. Some impacted specimens were also sectioned through the impact

zone with a wet diamond coated saw and polished using various micro powders. These were then viewed under a VMM200 microscope to determine the internal damage mechanisms.

DAMAGE AREA

The damage areas were determined from the C-scans (Fig. 3), where the dark area in the centre of the impact zone depicts a loss in signal during C-scanning which is a result of the permanent indentations and penetrations induced by the impacts. If multiple delaminations exist, the C-scanning will only determine the depth of the delamination closest to the top surface. It therefore does not provide any information about the size and depth of any delaminations below the first delamination encountered from the top surface. This resulted in the inability to determine the level of damage through each ply interface only the overall projected damage area.

Figure 3: Ultrasonic C-scans: (a) conical (4 J Lay-up 2), (b) ogival (4 J Lay-up 2), (c) hemispherical (4 J Lay-up 2), (d) conical (6 J Lay-up 2), (e) ogival (6 J Lay-up 2), (f) hemispherical (6 J Lay-up 2), (g) conical (6 J Lay-up 1), (h) ogival (6 J Lay-up 1), and (i) hemispherical (6 J Lay-up 1).

The total damage areas produced by the ogival and conical impactors were found to be similar except for the 6 J impacts on the lay-up 2 specimens where the ogival damage areas were nearer to those produced by the hemispherical impactor. These results support the prediction that as the impactor becomes blunter the damage area increases due to the increase in delamination. The increase in initial impact energy from 4 J to 6 J had a more pronounced effect on the total damage area produced by the ogival impactor compared to the other impactors.

The change in stacking sequence for the specimens impacted at an initial impact energy of 6 J caused a variation in the damage areas as can be seen in Fig. 4. The lay-up 1 specimens produced larger damage areas for the conical and hemispherical impactors but less for the ogival impactor.

The overall shape of the damage areas were found to be circular for all impacts as expected due to the woven nature of the carbon/epoxy laminates. This is characteristic of woven composite laminates which also restricts the growth of delaminations. This circular pattern is supported by the thermo-scan results (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Total damage areas for the carbon/epoxy specimens determined from C-scanning

A large advantage with flash thermography over other types of NDI techniques is the short time it takes to complete an inspection. The specimens were coated in a matt black paint in order to absorb more efficiently the heat generated by the flash lamps. The heat conducts from the surface through the part at a uniform rate until it encounters a discontinuity.

The thermo-scans for the specimens with permanent indentation or penetration after impact were clear in depicting the internal damage (Fig. 5). The results were not as clear for the specimens impacted at 4 J using a hemispherical impactor, which produced BVID (Fig. 5). This is a result of the internal damage in the specimens impacted by a hemispherical impactor being dominated by delamination. This will cause less difference in the heat dissipation levels through the thickness.

Damage areas were also determined from the thermo-scans and were found to vary significantly with the C-scans results. This was a result of the difficulty in interpreting the thermo-scans to define where the boundary of the damage exists. Although difficult to determine accurate damage areas using thermography, this method has the advantage of being a very fast method of NDI which clearly identifies the internal damage in the composite specimens.

Figure 5: Thermo-scans: (a) Conical (4 J), (b) ogival (4 J), and (c) hemispherical (4 J). For remaining thermo-scans please refer to Mitrevski et al.[1].

MICROSCOPY

Since the NDI techniques of C-scanning and thermography used in this study only display the overall damage area, micrographs were used to determine the internal damage mechanisms induced by the various impactor shapes. The internal damage mechanisms are of importance since they influence the residual strengths and energy absorption capabilities of the composite laminate.

The micrographs confirmed the previous results that the conical impactor produced the largest penetration depth followed by the ogival and hemispherical impactors respectively for all impact conditions. A common feature for all specimens was that the most extensive damage existed near the bottom plies due to the bending stresses experienced by the thin laminates.

Various damage mechanisms were identified from the micrographs as follows and displayed in Fig. 6.

1. Fibre breakage; determined from the four layers that are $0^\circ/90^\circ$ where the 90° fibres run parallel to the sectioned specimen;
2. Delamination; defined where a gap existed between ply interfaces;
3. Matrix cracking; defined by lines or cracks running through the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers and 0° fibres. Where the 0° fibres were circular whereas the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres were elliptical in the micrographs.

Figure 6: Various internal damage mechanisms identified in micrographs.

For the specimen impacted at 4 J by a conical impactor (Fig. 7(a)), there was extensive damage in the impact zone consisting of fibre breakage, delamination and matrix cracking. The post-impact thickness was larger than for the ogival and hemispherical impactors respectively. This was due to the larger back-face damage that occurred in the specimen impacted by the conical impactor as identified in Mitrevski et al. [1]. The specimen impacted at 4 J by a hemispherical impactor (Fig. 7(c)) consisted predominantly of matrix cracking and delamination in the top plies, whereas in the bottom plies, fibre breakage was visible and the most delamination and matrix cracking was observed out of all specimens impacted at 4 J. The delamination and matrix cracking progressed from the top ply to the bottom ply increasing radially from the point of impact. For the specimen impacted by the ogival impactor (Fig. 7(b)) at 4 J, a localised fibre breakage directly beneath the point of impact existed. The delamination sizes were similar to the specimens impacted by the conical impactor.

For the lay-up 2 specimens impacted at an initial impact energy of 6 J, the conical impactor (Fig. 7(d)) produced the largest level of fibre breakage followed by the ogival impactor (Fig. 7(e)). The post-impact thicknesses in all the 6 J specimens were very similar. This is related to the very similar levels of back-face damage that occurred as identified in Mitrevski et al. [1]. For the specimen impacted at 6 J by the hemispherical impactor (Fig. 7(f)) a few cracks were evident in the top layer however, the fibres were largely intact. The three remaining layers with fibres running parallel to the direction of the cut specimen were broken. The lay-up 2 specimens impacted at 6 J acquired similar damage characteristics to the lay-up 1 specimens impacted at 6 J.

The specimens impacted by the conical impactor absorbed the most energy followed by the ogival and hemispherical impactors, respectively, as discussed in Mitrevski et al. [1]. This can be attributed to the increase in energy required to break the fibres and penetrate the specimen where less energy is required to initiate delamination.

Figure 7: Micrographs of the impact zone in specimens; (a) conical (4 J Lay-up 2), (b) ogival (4 J Lay-up 2), (c) hemispherical (4 J Lay-up 2), (d) conical (6 J Lay-up 2), (e) ogival (6 J Lay-up 2), (f) hemispherical (6 J Lay-up 2), (g) conical (6 J Lay-up 1), (h) ogival (6 J Lay-up 1), and (i) hemispherical (6 J Lay-up 1).

Sections were also cut approximately 2 mm (saw blade thickness) from the central impact point to determine the level of damage away from the impact point. This was completed only for the lay-up 2 specimens impacted at 4 J and 6 J with the micrographs shown in Fig. 8.

For the specimens impacted at an initial impact energy of 4 J by the conical impactor (Fig. 8(a)), a small level of delamination existed through the thickness, however, the overall thickness of the specimen at this point remained unchanged. Delamination and matrix cracking was found in the top and bottom plies of the specimens impacted by the hemispherical impactor (Fig. 8(c)). Delamination through the thickness and fibre breakage at the bottom ply was found for the specimen impacted by the ogival impactor (Fig. 8(b)). For the specimens impacted at an initial impact energy of 6 J, the conical impactor (Fig. 8(d)) produced fibre breakage and delamination at the bottom plies. The hemispherical and ogival impactors (Fig. 8(e) & (f)) produced the most extensive damage with all fibre breakage,

matrix cracking and delamination occurring validating the larger damage areas found from the C-scans. Delamination dominated in the specimens impacted by the hemispherical impactor whereas more fibre breakage was found in the specimens impacted by the ogival impactor.

Figure 8: Micrographs 2 mm from the impact zone in specimens; (a) conical (4 J Lay-up 2), (b) ogival (4 J Lay-up 2), (c) hemispherical (4 J Lay-up 2), (d) conical (6 J Lay-up 2), (e) ogival (6 J Lay-up 2), and (f) hemispherical (6 J Lay-up 2).

OVERALL DAMAGE LENGTH

The damage lengths were measured from the micrographs from where the damage begins and ends on either side of the impact point. This measurement was then compared to the damage length taken from the corresponding ultrasonic C-scans to validate the NDI results.

Figure 9: Comparison between cross sectional damage length determined from C-scans and micrographs.

It was difficult to determine the exact end points of the damage due to various factors such as voids and externally applied damage from the cutting and polishing. However, very good agreement was found between the micrographs and C-scans thereby validating the damage areas obtained from the C-scans as can be seen from Fig. 9.

CONCLUSIONS

A post-impact analysis of carbon/epoxy laminates impacted by various impactor shapes has been investigated. NDI and destructive inspection techniques were used to analyse the effect of various impactor shapes on the damage to composite laminates under low-velocity impact conditions, yielding the following conclusions:

- The hemispherical impactor produced the largest damage area in all instances. This was followed by ogival and conical impactors, respectively, for all impact conditions except the 6 J impacts on the lay-up 1 specimens where the conical impactor produced a slightly larger damage area than the ogival impactor.
- The damage areas calculated from the thermo-scans did not agree well with the C-scan results. This was due to difficulties associated with defining the boundary of the damage area accurately in the thermo-scans. This requires further investigation.
- The overall damage shape was found to be circular by both NDI techniques as expected.
- From the micrographs, the hemispherical impactor produced the most delamination and the conical impactor produced the most fibre breakage. The damage caused by the conical impactor was more localised, which agreed with the NDI results.
- Most damage was located near the bottom plies due to the extensive bending stresses experienced by the thin laminates.

Different impactor shapes produced different levels of the individual damage components, such as fibre breakage, matrix cracking and delamination, to occur. In future work, specimens will be subjected to tensile loading which will determine what effects the different levels of these internal damage mechanisms have on the residual strength of the composite laminates. Additionally, future studies will consider the effects of in-plane pre-stress on the same parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Mr David Rowlands, Dr Nik Rajic and Mr Howard Morton from DSTO for their assistance with the thermography and ultrasonic C-scanning Mr Noel Goldsmith, also from DSTO, with the microscopy.

REFERENCES

1. Mitrevski, T., Marshall, I.H., Thomson, R., Jones, R., and Whittingham, B. "The effect of impactor shape on the impact response of composite laminates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 67, No. 2, 2005, pp. 139-148.
2. Abrate, S. "Impact on Laminated Composite Materials", *Applied Mechanics Review*, Vol. 44, No. 4, 1991, pp. 155-190.
3. Caprino, G. "Residual strength prediction of impacted CFRP laminates", *Composite Materials*, Vol. 18, 1984, pp.508-518.
4. Davies, G.A.O., Hitchings, D., and Zhou, G. "Impact damage and residual strengths of woven fabric glass/polyester laminates", *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, Vol. 27A, 1996, pp. 1147-1156.

5. Cantwell, W.J. and Morton, J. "Comparison of the low and high velocity impact response of CFRP", *Composites*, Vol. 20, No. 6, 1989, pp. 545-551.
6. Prichard, J.C. and Hogg, P.J. "The role of impact damage in post-impact compression testing", *Composites*, Vol. 21, No. 6, 1990, pp. 503-509.
7. Hitchen, S.A. and Kemp, R.M.J. "The effect of stacking sequence on impact damage in a carbon fibre/epoxy composite", *Composites*, Vol. 26, No. 3, 1995, pp. 207-214.
8. Benzeggagh, M.L. and Benmedakhene, S. "Residual strength of a glass/polypropylene composite material subjected to impact", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 55, 1995, pp. 1-11.
9. Lee, S.M., Cheon, J.S., and Im, Y.T. "Experimental and numerical study of the impact behavior of SMC plates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 47, 1999, pp. 551-561.
10. Zhou, G., Lloyd, J.C. and McGuirk, J.J. "Experimental evaluation of geometric factors affecting damage mechanisms in carbon/epoxy plates", *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, Vol. 32, 2001, pp. 71-84.
11. Mines, R.A.W., Roach, A.M., Jones, N. "High velocity perforation behaviour of polymer composite laminates", *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 22, 1999, pp. 561-588.
12. Shyr, T. and Pan, Y. "Impact resistance and damage characteristics of composite laminates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 62, 2003, pp. 193-203.
13. Cantwell, W.J. and Morton, J. "Comparison of the low and high velocity impact response of CFRP", *Composites*, Vol. 20, No. 6, 1989, pp. 545-551.
14. Cantwell, W.J. and Morton, J. "Impact perforation of carbon fiber reinforced plastic", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 38, 1990, pp. 119-141.
15. Sjoblom, P.O., Hartness, J.T. and Cordell, T.M. "On low-velocity impact testing of composite materials", *Composite Materials*, Vol. 22, 1988, pp. 30-52.
16. Baker, A.A., Callus, P.J., Georgiadis, S., Falzon, P.J., Dutton, S.E. and Leong, K.H. "An affordable methodology for replacing metallic aircraft panels with advanced composites", *Composites A*, Vol. 35, No. 5, 2002, pp. 687-696.
17. Whittingham, B., Marshall, I.H., Mitrevski, T., and Jones, R. "The response of composite structures with pre-stress subject to low velocity impact damage", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 66, 2004, pp. 685-698.